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I. Language Profile

- ? 10 or fewer speakers today (ethnologue.com)
- ? contact languages: Chuckchansi (Yokuts) villages with inhabitants of both groups; intermarriage (exogamous moiety system)
- ? language status: bilingualism in English
- ? language prospects: nearly extinct
- ? structural results: some borrowing from Spanish; borrowing from English

II. Syllable

Default syllable template

- ? syllable canon is notable rigid
- ? (when length treated as C) only two syllable types: CV (short syllable) and CVC (long syllable)
- ? syllable length \neq phonemic length
- ? one of the first two syllables of any form is always a long syllable
- ? all syllables occurring immediately before any type of juncture are long every Miwok word contains one long syllable
- ? except that at least one of the first two syllables of a word is always long, the occurrence of long and short syllables has not been found to fall into any particular patterns
- ? sequences of up to five long syllables have been found (including forms containing no short syllables; e.g. /tyntyn:e/nɣ:lek/ 'your thinking, then')
- ? long sequences of short syllables are rarer
- ? long syllables more frequent in connected discourse than short ones
- ? a word ends with the last long syllable before primary stress
- ? all word-final syllables are long
- ? each word having one primary stress
- ? short syllable before primary stress belongs to the next word
- ? words begin with long syllables with primary stress or with short syllables weakly stressed followed by a long with primary stress
- ? all long syllables after the first bear secondary stress
- ? roots always begins with C + V (roots always monomorphemic) no roots with less than these two phonemes; many monosyllabic, majority consists of no more than two syllables
- ? a monosyllabic as a minimal free form particles, e.g. /jej/ 'hey!', /ken/ 'no; not', //a:/ 'interrogative (calling for yes-no answer)', //o:/ 'oh', and //yh/ 'grunt (exclamation of minor discomfort)'

Phonotactic Patterns:

- ? Cs occur singly in initial and final position
- ? Cs occur singly and in two-member clusters in medial position **no onset clusters, but morpheme-final clusters canonical base forms: /CV:-/, /CVCC-/, /CVCVH-/, /CVCCV-/, and /CVCV:C-/ (but not within a syllable!)**

- ☐ no initial or final C-clusters and
- ☐ no clusters of more than two members
- ☐ no Vs in initial or final position **no v-initial syllable or word, but morphemes (allomorphs of certain suffixes), e.g. /hywa:-t-ak-Ø/ > [.hy.wa:.tak.] 'I run just now.', /hywa:-t-eH-// > [.hy.wa:.te/] 'run!' only with resyllabification!**
- ☐ no V-clusters
- ☐ no /N/ and /:/ in initial position (/:/ length; continuation of the preceding V or C treated as C); /N/ in onset position word-medially, e.g. /naN:a// 'man', /heNiNe:/ 'to get lost'
- ☐ no /:/ intervocally in medial position **long Cs (C:) and long Vs (V:) in word medial position resyllabification: length of /C:/ as onset of following syllable, length of /V:/ as coda of the same syllable (e.g. //e.sel.:y-/ 'child' CVCVC:V > .CV.CVC.:V)**
- ☐ no /sʈ/ (the rarest C) in final position **but in coda position word-medially, e.g. /tosʈpu:/ 'to get stiff', /husʈta:/ 'to make tight'**
- ☐ /t/ and /sʈ/ particularly rare in clusters (in any case rare phonemes)
- ☐ no /ʃt/ but /tʃ/ gaps (appear to be fortuitous)
- ☐ within one syllable no /sʈ/ **before the Vs /i/, /u/, or /y/ or after /a/, /e/, or /y/**
- ☐ final C of a long syllable can be any C, including length
- ☐ except in initial syllables, length can take the place of any of the Cs in the above formulae

English loans:

- ☐ /b, d, g, f, jʃ, r/ only in loan words (principally English)
- ☐ initial C-clusters (e.g. /krɪsmas/ 'Christmas')
- ☐ triconsonantal medial clusters (e.g. /kɔ:sgɔ:l/ 'Coarsegold')
- ☐ (rarely) final C-clusters (e.g. /kɔ:l/ 'kerosene')

III. Tone & Stress

Stress

- ☐ in isolated forms, primary stress falls on the first long syllable
- ☐ secondary stress falls on succeeding long syllables (present on final syllables, since they are always long)
- ☐ in a long sequence of long syllables, the even-numbered ones tend to be less heavily stressed than the odd-numbered ones, counting from the beginning of the long-syllable sequence
- ☐ short syllables carry weak stress

Tone system (*system of pitch accent*)

- ☐ three nonphonemic pitch levels, occurrence connected with juncture
- ☐ in forms given in isolation (before final juncture) syllables with primary stress are on level 2
- ☐ any preceding short syllable is on level 1 (lowest pitch)
- ☐ pitch rises to level 3 on a late long syllable and drops to 1 on the final syllable

IV. "Free" Grammatical Morphemes

Clitics and particles *I don't know, if they're correct here!*

- ☐ the use of particles largely a matter of style, certain of them much more frequent in conversation than in narrative texts

- ☐ particles are monomorphemic words
 - ☐ as morphemes they have the following characteristics:
 - they are roots rather than suffixes, since they sometimes occur in utterance-initial position
 - the only suffixes which ever follow them are postfixes
 - with one exception (Ñho/:ajÑ ~ Ñho/:aj:y:Ñ 'and') they exhibit no allomorphy
 - ☐ as words their distinguishing features are:
 - meet phonological criteria for words: each having primary stress on the first long syllable
 - meet morphological criteria, since in utterance-medial position they are found between the final suffix of the preceding word and the root of the following word
 - found in the same form at beginning/end of utterances
 - not all, but three can be elicited in isolation: /hy:/ 'yes', /ken/ 'no', /jej/ 'hey!' occur sometimes as complete utterances
 - particularly differ from nouns and verbs in that they contain no medial, prefinal or final suffixes
 - frequently follow the word they modify
 - short; and many have meanings hard to identify
- renders them somewhat difficult to distinguish from postfixes distinction can be made by careful attention to the phonological characteristics which mark them as words, and by the fact that even those which cannot be elicited in isolation are sometimes found at the beginning of utterances

V. Polymorphemic forms

Phonological processes across (any kind of) morpheme boundaries

- ☐ when identical Cs are juxtaposed, the cluster is phonemically /C:/, e.g. ÑneH-Ñ (demonstrative stem) 'here' + Ñ-/Ñ (nominative case) + Ñ-/okÑ (postfix; meaning unknown) ÑneH-/okÑ /ne/:ok/ 'this one' *resyllabification: /ne/.:ok./*
- ☐ morphophoneme ÑHÑ = phonemically /:/ ~ /Ø/, zero when:
 - (i) followed by one C followed by any type of juncture or
 - (ii) followed or preceded by a C-cluster, except when a morpheme ending ÑVHÑ is followed by one beginning ÑCHÑ, in which case /V:C/ is found
 - (iii) otherwise it is /:/
- ☐ morphophonemic sequence ÑijÑ phonemically /i:/, e.g. Ñhal-ki-Ñ 'to hunt' + Ñ-j-Ñ (fut.) + Ñ-te-Ñ (1.p.sg. Series 2 pron. suf.) + Ñ-/Ñ (nom. case) Ñhal-ki-j-te-/Ñ /halki:te// 'I shall hunt.'
- ☐ morphophoneme ÑXÑ phonemically /:/ ~ /Ø/
 - (i) /:/ when followed by a single C and none precedes, but its position, as length, is after the following C (ÑVXCVÑ /VC:V/; ÑVXHCÑ /VC:V/)
 - (ii) otherwise ÑXÑ is zero
 - (iii) e.g. Ñ/enpu-Ñ 'to chase' + Ñ-koX-Ñ (imperative) + Ñ-mah:i:Ñ (1.P.pl.excl., Ser.4) //enpukom:ah:i/ 'let's chase him!'
- ☐ morphophoneme ÑYÑ phonemically /y/ ~ /u/ ~ /o/:
 - (i) when the preceding syllable contains /u/, ÑYÑ is /u/
 - (ii) when the preceding syllable contains /o/, ÑYÑ is /u/ ~ /o/, while ÑY:Ñ is /u:/
 - (iii) elsewhere ÑYÑ appears as /y/
- ☐ the morphophoneme ÑYÑ occurs at the morpheme boundary, i.e. between two morphemes, when:
 - (i) a morpheme ending in one or more Cs is followed either by a morpheme

consisting of one C followed by juncture, or by a morpheme beginning with two Cs (except for the cluster $\tilde{N}CH\tilde{N}$)

(ii) a morpheme ending in two Cs (except for the cluster $\tilde{N}HC\tilde{N}$) is followed by one beginning with a C

this morphophoneme intervenes between morphemes whenever their juxtaposition could be expected to give rise to either a cluster of more than two members or to a final cluster, unless the cluster can be avoided by $\tilde{N}H\tilde{N}$ occurring as zero

☐ consonantal alternation: /s/ in the augmentative or "normal-size" form, and /c/ in the diminutive form; very few cases of this alternation

e.g. $\tilde{N}/esel:y-\tilde{N}$ 'child' vs. $\tilde{N}/ecel:y-\tilde{N}$ 'baby'

sometimes no diminutive-augmentative significance, no difference in meaning

e.g. $\tilde{N}mu:sa-\tilde{N} \sim \tilde{N}mu:ca-\tilde{N}$ 'to be ashamed'

Degree and types of fusion

☐ concatenative, phonologically bound morphemes

☐ exclusively suffixing

☐ each word contains as its first morpheme (only!) one of the class of roots

roots define the beginning of a word

☐ (except in the case of particles) the root is always followed by one or more suffixes

☐ all words (except particles) end with at least one member of the class of final suffixes or with final suffix(es) + one or more postfixes

☐ no morpheme member of both classes (root and suffix)

☐ suffixes are less subject to canonical restrictions, since (1) they also do not occur in first morphemic position and (2) morpheme boundaries within the word do not necessarily correspond to syllabic divisions

they consist of any phoneme or sequence of phonemes that conforms to the rules of canonical form

some are single phonemes, and few contain more than two syllables

☐ root always monomorphemic, consisting of the initial morpheme of the word and nothing more

root allomorphy determined by the phonological and morphemic environment provided by the first following suffix

☐ stems mono- or bi-morphemic, i.e. some root alone, some root + one suffix, e.g. /wel:-/ 'to fetch' root/stem, /wel-ki-/ 'to fetch' stem (root + verbal suffix)

☐ bases mono-, bi-, or polymorphemic, e.g. /wel-ki-jik:-/ 'to go to fetch' (stem + verbal suffix, andative); allomorphs: /-j:-/, /-j-/ (/ja:-/ stems end in V, /a:-/ stems end in C)

☐ themes mono-, bi-, or polymorphemic

a theme + one or more final suffixes constitutes a complete word

any of the following types of composition:

a. a suitable allomorph of a root;

b. a suitable stem-type;

c. a base plus a modal suffix; or

d. a base or a previously-formed theme plus one or more suffixes

Word structure:

☐ root (+ suffix) = stem + (medial suffix(es)) = base + prefinal suffix(es) = theme

+ final suffix(es) + (postfix(es))

Suffix classes:

- ☐ nominal suffixes particularity: as with verbal suffixes, the stem-form sometimes calls for a second V or a third C, which is not present in related stems in other environments
 - (i) position of second V filled by ÑYÑ
 - (ii) position of third C usually filled by Ñ/Ñ, but in some instances length is found
- ☐ medial suffixes: not obligatory, most derivational meanings
- ☐ prefinal suffixes: tense, aspect; diminutive suffix; some case suffixes not obligatory; 3 modal suffixes obligatory
- ☐ final suffixes: always on verbal and nominal themes; inflectional suffixes; case and personal pronominal suffixes obligatory (with respect to verbs and nouns); nine case suffixes (4 autonomous; 4 subordinate, i.e. always followed by an allomorph of one of the autonomous ones; one possessive, can function either as auto. or subord.)
- ☐ postfixes: not obligatory; two or more sometimes in sequence; also following particles; meanings are diverse:
 - (i) some have interjectional character (compare engl. 'then, well, though, isn't it?')
 - (ii) others indicate different kinds of questions
 - (iii) some extremely difficult to translate precisely
 - (iv) one Ñ-/ekÑ has temporal meaning 'past' (follows verbs which normally refer only to present tenses)
 - prominent feature of conversational style, although all but a few are uncommon in narrative texts except for quoted speech
 - affixes because: (1) do not meet phonological criteria for independent words; (2) they cannot be elicited in isolation; (3) no utterance can commence with a member of this class; and (4) members of this class not followed by any of final suffixes
 - in some cases, they appear to be in immediate constituency with more than the form whose final suffixes they follow
 - they are thus of the nature of postclitics
 - sometimes a definite sequence of postfixes
 - certain always follow others, and never precede them
 - completely invariable in form none with more than one allomorph, even the morphophonemes ÑYÑ and ÑHÑ (which occur frequently elsewhere) haven't been found in postfixes

VIII. Reduplication

- ☐ stem types (= reduplication, total and partial) (+ verbal or nominal suffixes):
 - (i) C₁V₁C₂C₁V₁C₂⁻, e.g. /uk/uk- nY- 'to go in and out the rooms', cf. /u:k- 'to enter' [reduplication of the whole stem](#)
 - (ii) C₁V₁C₂C₃V₂C₃⁻, e.g. joh/u/- nY- 'to kill here and there', cf. jo:h- 'to kill' [reduplication of the last C \(or the C of the last syllable\) of the stem](#)
 - (iii) C₁V₁C₂V₂C₃V₂C₃⁻, e.g. hylet:et:- 'to flop about (of fish)', cf. hyle:t- 'to jump; to fly' [red. of the last syllable](#)
 - (iv) C₁V₁C₂V₂C₃V₂⁻, e.g. hel:a:ja- m:a 'one who is easily scared, a coward', cf. hela:j- 'to scare' [red. of the last V/V of the last syllable](#)
 - (v) C₁V₁C₂V₁C₂
 - (vi) C₁V₁C₂C₁V₁C₂, mostly onomatopoeica, animal or plant names, not

productive